

Situating the Exploitation of Female Migrant Domestic Workers in the Gulf States: A Case Study of Saudi Arabia

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There has been a persistent increase in the population of migrant domestic workers (MDW), which are mostly women, in the Gulf Council Cooperation (GCC) countries since the 1980s. While they form an integral part of a Gulf household which has come to rely heavily on their labour, the MDWs have been conspicuously left out of the protection of labour laws. On the other hand, their public counterparts, working outside of the household, irrespective of the gender, are covered within a code of labour laws. Under the operation of the Kafala sponsorship system and in the absence of legal protection, MDWs remain highly vulnerable to abuse by their employers. The paper argues that such a peculiarity has arisen due to an intersection of varied phenomena, viz., the sanctity of the private space as against the public space which hinders the former from being recognised as a work space; the invisibility of the work done by women within the domestic sphere; and a 'silent pact' between the Gulf states and citizens which allows the former to exchange citizens' political freedom for unhindered 'enjoyment of life'. Indeed, an outright exclusion of MDWs from protective laws was possible because it is a sector dominated by women, migrating from countries where similar notions of the public-private divide and invisible labour prevailed. The paper takes a case study approach involving the case of Saudi Arabia to find patterns of exploitation and generalise for the larger GCC region.

Introduction

A growing demand of domestic employment in the Gulf Council states (Saudi Arabia, UAE, Bahrain, Qatar, Oman, Kuwait) owing to the rising wealth and living standards have created a large influx of migrant population. According to ILO, "as many as 21 million people, predominantly women were employed in the GCC countries in 2010" and the numbers have been increasing since then. In most GCC nations, the migrant population outnumbers the native population, with the former accounting for as much as 87 percent in Qatar and as little as 21 percent in Oman. Saudi Arabia has the highest demand for migrant domestic workers in the GCC, followed by Kuwait. The women employed in these countries are largely from South and Southeast Asian countries of India, Sri Lanka, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Philippines, and Indonesia where the discriminatory nature of employment and patriarchal understanding of women's labour had already pushed the working women to the margins of the economic sector. In most of the situations these women earn about more than four times of what they would have earned in their home countries for a similar nature of work. This has propelled a massive migrant influx into the GCC. However, such increase in wages come at a great cost to these women. Multiple factors, both unique to the Gulf states, and general, negatively affect the human rights of migrant domestic workers.

The kafala (sponsorship) system, unique to the region, which is founded on historical hospitality of Bedouin ideals controlling the treatment and protection of foreign guests, is used by countries in the region to manage this massive influx of migrant workers. This has grown formalised through time in the various national legal frameworks that determine the terms of migrant workers' residence and employment, and the kafala system now rules the

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lives of the majority of migrant workers in the Mashreq and GCC countries. Employers are referred to as kafeels (sponsors) in the kafala system, and they define their labour need and meet it either directly or through intermediaries such as private employment agencies (PEAs). As a result of their employers' extensive influence over their legal position in the country, such workers are prone to abuse and exploitation. However, not all workers are equally exploited: some are more than the others. The conspicuous nature of such a system puts particular burden on the domestic migrant workers as they are explicitly excluded from any of the labour laws which protect their non-domestic counterparts. While domestic work often comes in the form of informal work in many countries of the world leading to evasion of rights of the workers, what is peculiar in GCC states is the formal and official nature of the employment and yet fundamental exclusion from any sorts of protections. This is primarily due to the consideration that domestic workers are members of the *kafil's* family, a part of the private space which has certain notions of sanctity attached to it under the Islamic jurisprudence. Furthermore, the exploitative nature of domestic work often goes unnoticed owing to the non-recognition of domestic work as an "economic" activity. The conventional way of doing economics has often kept the ambit of private out of its purview. This has resulted in an utter disregard for the productive work done within the bounds of home. Household thus becomes an invisible space of economic activity. Further exacerbating the situation is the fact that the patriarchal nature of the social order tends to undervalue the work performed by women. This renders the work done by these women as invisible.

Adding to the exploitative dynamics is the discrimination against non-citizens prevailing in these states. With large percentage of migrant population flooding these countries, the citizens often feel overwhelmed by the foreign presence. This has resulted in racial discrimination and xenophobia amongst the natives (Roper 2008). However, while the public opinion is against the in-migration of foreigners, there is a simultaneous need for more workers to fuel the economy and maintain the luxurious life the natives have become used to. Migrants, the subject of hatred, then become some sort of a necessary evil. This has resulted in a highly visible migrant domestic population to be treated as second class humans, and forcefully 'invisibilised'.

The result of such 'invisibilisation' has been noted in the conditions with which the domestic workers meet upon their employment. The exploitation of the workers begins from their home countries. The absence of a contract and/or contract substitution is a serious difficulty for domestic employees in terms of contractual obligations. There are frequently no contracts written between the employer and the employee, and where a contract does exist, the domestic worker is unaware of the employer's terms and conditions; and/or the contract is signed by intermediaries without the worker's awareness (Tomei and Belser 2011). Domestic workers' passports are frequently taken away from them by their employers once they reach in the destination country. They are forced to do several types of labour not just within the employer's home, but also in other houses to which they are 'loaned', without any clear indication of the type of work to be done or even set working hours (Blanchet 2002). They are nearly typically expected to deliver these additional services without further pay. They are frequently denied contact with their family and placed in social isolation from other domestic workers or acquaintances, in addition to different forms of cruelty. Employers frequently justify such a limitation by claiming that it reduces the likelihood of domestic workers departing before their contract term is over. Domestic workers are often neglected by their home country, with indeterminate hours of work, no off-days, non-payment of salaries, psychological, verbal, physical, and sexual abuse, and movement restrictions (Roper 2008).

Review of the Literature

Aaserud, et al. (2013) have prepared a report exploring abuses in the countries of origin and destination through a case study approach including Philippines and Kuwait. The report takes a detailed look at migrant domestic workers as they prepare to leave the Philippines, as well as their working circumstances in Kuwait and their return home. Assessing the history of labour migration to Kuwait, as well as the economic variables that lead to labour migration from the Philippines, provides historical context. The research investigates abuses throughout the process and gives recommendations and solutions based on the nations of origin and destination, as well as international legal norms, with a special emphasis on the 2011 ILO Domestic Workers Convention (No. 189). Prosecution of those who mistreat domestic migrant workers, reforms in Kuwaiti legislation and policy, the implementation of protection measures in Kuwait, and the establishment and strengthening of civil society initiatives are among the recommendations.

Abimourched (2011) has presented a rights-based regulatory framework to deal migrant workers in the Mashriq region. She aims to convey a complicated and nuanced picture of female domestic workers' vital economic role and bad working circumstances not only in the Mashriq, but also in their home countries. MDWs are relegated to the periphery of society, she observes, despite the fact that they provide care, cook, and clean for relatively well-off households. MDWs' rights are violated and discriminated due to a lack of regulatory framework and government control. Ms. Abimourched also gives an intriguing comparison of the legislative frameworks governing the recruitment and employment of MDWs in Jordan, Lebanon, and Syria, as well as their strengths and drawbacks.

Anbesse et al. (2009) has linked migration to mental health through a study of Ethiopian women working in the Gulf states. Exploitative treatment, enforced cultural isolation, weakening cultural identity, and disappointment in not meeting expectations were all identified as serious hazards to mental health by Anbesse et al. Self-affirmation of cultural identity and the establishment of socio-cultural supports were said to help counteract the other negative forces.

Beydoun (2006) has dealt with the issue of trafficking of Ethiopian Workers into Lebanon through an in-depth study of the Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons. He notes that, at the time of writing, the international community had not made a concerted effort to combat the trafficking of women for domestic labour in this case, and he offers a critique of legal, policy, and grassroots-based measures that have been or could be taken to improve conditions for Ethiopian domestic workers.

Madhavi (2010) has placed the issue of trafficking, especially for sex work, in a theoretical framework presented through critical perspective. Her essay refutes the concept that Iranian sex workers in Dubai are simply victims of human trafficking. Instead, the author explains how these stories were produced and frequently misread by academics. The "feminization of migration" language, according to Ms. Mahdavi, has skewed the complicated realities of forced labour, migration, and sex work. She claims that this rhetoric does not reflect Iranian women's actual experiences with migrating to Dubai or their motivations for doing so. She goes on to say that feminization language "perpetuates gendered and raced discourses on the movement of women's bodies, which are widespread in international discourses on sex work and trafficking." Ms. Mahdavi conducts qualitative ethnographic fieldwork to analyse sex workers', migrant women's, and service providers' experiences and perceptions of agency.

Manseau (2006) has provided contractual solutions for migrant labourers and has looked at the domestic and international responses to the abuse of female domestic migrant workers in the Gulf states. Domestic workers are poorly safeguarded by cultural and legal frameworks in both receiving and exporting nations, according to Manseau. She concludes that a standard working contract would provide workers more negotiating power, allow for more equitable and effective access to justice, and encourage judicial decision enforcement. Despite arguments to the contrary based on Shari'a law, she believes that Arab states are compelled under international law to monitor the private sector in order to prevent employer abuse of workers.

Varia (2011) has looked at some of the recent reforms that has taken place to protect migrant domestic workers in the Gulf states. She claims that a combination of major labour law gaps, immigration restrictions, and public acceptance of discrimination against migrant workers results in widespread human rights breaches, including modern slavery. Ms. Varia mentions some of the modest improvements implemented by successive governments, but she points out that the majority of them have not implemented complete reforms. She notes that opposition to reforms stems from concerns about rising expenses, lost revenue for businesses, and perceived security dangers.

The exploitation of female migrant domestic workers in the Gulf states is a well-documented fact that has attracted numerous scholarly interventions. However, most of the work that has been done on the subject are under the auspices of International Labour Organisation which has created most of the prevailing literature in the form of reports. Also evident from the literature is their problem-solving approach which takes the exploitation at its face value. This has also prevented a thematic continuity in the literature as the policy reports have been on varied issue areas related to the overall well-being of the migrant workers. The purpose of the reports has been to suggest policy implications to the Gulf states as well as the home states of the migrants. There has not been sufficient attempt to theoretically situate the exploitation of female migrant domestic workers and expose its underlying causes in the first place. The reports have also missed on the distinction between the nature of exploitation of domestic and non-domestic labour. The literature is thus, remedial in nature without exploring the causations. The present paper aims at amending this gap by situating the exploitation of female migrant domestic workers in a theoretical position.

The focus area of the paper is the Gulf state of Saudi Arabia, though the Kafala sponsorship system prevails in the entire Mashriq region which includes Jordan and Lebanon as well. However, these two states have initiated reforms to include female domestic workers under the purview of labour laws. These states have seen a large influx of refugee population which have been to some extent integrated with the mainstream society. The sort of xenophobia and hatred for foreigners seen in the Gulf states is not witnessed in Jordan and Lebanon. These differing circumstances has evaded the inclusion of these states from the scope of the study.

The scope of the paper is limited to study of female domestic migrant labour, though a small proportion of domestic labour also includes males who are not included under the labour laws and face exploitation in terms of unpaid overwork and racial discrimination. They are mainly occupied as drivers, gardeners and handymen. However, their labour is not taken to be invisible as though within the household sector, jobs performed by men are taken as work in the proper sense. Also, they are not isolated within the home premises like their female counterparts and most of the male employees reside out of the employer's house. This makes their situation less precarious than women who are constantly at the mercy of their

employers for basic provisions too. This is not to say that the exploitation of males does not require a similar study, however this paper has attempted to take a feminist standpoint to revisit the idea of invisibility of labour and how it complicates the situations when interplayed with other discriminative tendencies.

Research Question and Hypothesis

Central Question:

) Why are Domestic Migrant Workers (DMWs) excluded from the protection of labour laws in the Gulf Council States?

Hypothesis:

) The exploitation of DMWs occur due to intersection of three interlinking phenomena, viz., invisibility of female labour, invisibility of private space in economic terms and invisibility of the migrant workers in the Gulf states.

Variables:

-) Dependent Variable: Exploitation of Domestic Migrant Workers (A)
-) Independent Variable₁: Invisibility of female labour (B₁)
-) Independent Variable₂: Invisibility of private space in economic terms (B₂)
-) Independent Variable₃: Invisibility of migrant workers in the Gulf states (B₃)
-) Antecedent Variable₁: Existence of patriarchal notions (x₁)
-) Antecedent Variable₂: Xenophobic tendencies against migrant labour (x₂)
-) Conditional Variable: Neglect of human rights by countries of origin and destination (y)
-) Intervening Variable: High Vulnerability of female DMWs (z)

Causal Mechanism:

The existing conditions of patriarchy (x₁) and xenophobic tendencies in the Gulf states (x₂), sets the stage for invisibility of female labour (B₁) linked to invisibility of private space (B₂), and invisibility of migrant labour (B₃). This increases the vulnerability of female migrant domestic labour (z) which is when conditioned by neglect of their human rights by states of origin and destination (y) leads to exploitation (A).

Tracing the Historicity of Kafala Sponsorship System in Islamic Law

While much research has been undertaken, mostly critical of the *kafala* as a system of oppression and exploitation of migrant labour in the GCC, there seems to be a consensus that there is no relationship at all between the traditional Islamic concept of *kafala* and its current application. In other words, it is argued that there is no evidence of a “genealogy” that links the Islamic jurisprudence of *kafala* to its contemporary forms (Franz 2011: 98). In a recent paper on the origins of the *kafala* related to migrant labour in the GCC, the historian, Al Shehabi (2019), provides documentary evidence showing how the British colonial rulers, first in Bahrain and later other GCC states from the 1920s, introduced what was for them a system of sponsorship and surety, but which was perfectly compatible with and adaptable to the principles of *kafala* in Islamic law and custom. It was, he argues, a “cheap” means of controlling foreigners and having local citizens take responsibility for them. Thus, there was no conscious decision on the part of the Muslim rulers of the region to apply the traditional form of *kafala* under new circumstances in the GCC that required massive numbers of foreign companies and workers. Rather, in this situation, the conflation of colonial rule and Islamic custom came together serendipitously.

The term “*kaf la*” has a wide semantic scope in Arabic. Its root word means to feed, support, vouch for or warrant; hence “*kafala*” refers to bail, guaranty, security or sponsorship (Wehr 1994: 976). According to Lane’s nineteenth century Arabic dictionary, *kafala* mean

“responsibility; answerableness; amenability; or suretyship; the conjoining of responsibility to another” (Jureidini and Hassan 2020). Likewise, the *kaf l* is “one who is responsible, answerable, amendable, or a sponsor or surety” (ibid.). In the Islamic tradition, *Kafala* is a significant concept that has its social, moral and business dimensions. *Kafala* thus originally refers to a contract where a guarantor conjoins a guaranteed person (*makf l*) and assumes liability for that person in various specified terms. *Kafala* is meant to provide an assurance of the fulfilment of an obligation of the guaranteed person.

Kafala contracts were used to protect the weak and vulnerable by instituting the patronage of a prominent local who provided whatever protection was required—a form of community responsibility for financial, legal or political representation (Franz 2014, 99). As such, the similarity between the classical Islamic usage of *kafala* and the new form as applied to the management of foreign workers has been seen as a merely linguistic one that lends it a “veneer of legitimacy,” i.e., the presence of a *kaf l* as guarantor (now sponsor) who would guarantee the legal residency of the foreigner who will abide by the rules of a contract and the laws of the country. As Franz observes, If the current use of the *kafala* system for migrant labour did descend from these earlier forms, it diverged dramatically in the context of nation states and neoliberal market forces and transformed into a system whereby non-nationals are bound to nationals for the purposes of work or business. (Franz 2014, 100).

The most highly critiqued issues of the contemporary *kafala* have indeed centred around the power, control and exploitation of the *kaf l* over foreign employees as well as business establishments. The criticisms have primarily been based on international human and labour rights law and conventions (International Labour Organization 2013). On the other hand, investigating the technical usage and application of the classical Islamic *kafala* system, it is clear that an essential element of the classical system is that *kafala* is considered a contract without benefits on the part of the guarantor. That is, the service of the guarantor (*kaf l*) is meant to be free of charge. It is in this sense that the new *kafala* may seem to violate a key traditional Islamic condition and may be seen more as a business-oriented system rather than one of trust and protection. A *kaf l* sponsors a worker and represents him/ her on behalf of the state on the condition that this specific worker will sign a contract to work for him or for others in return for certain benefits. It is not a pure *kafala* system. It is a *kafala-cum-ij ra* (sponsorship-cum-hiring) system, and in this sense the *kafala-makf l* relationship has been reversed where the *makf l* guarantees the fulfillment of a labour contract with the *kaf l* who pays the *makf l* for his/her labour, presumably making a profit from the labour. This new relationship is no longer *kafala* (Jureidini and Hassan 2020).

Although the original idea may have been for GCC citizens to take responsibility for the presence of foreigners, particularly professionals in the energy industries, the system quickly metamorphosed into one where the *kaf l* was not held responsible or accountable. For example, the *kaf l* is the one responsible for the obtaining of a work visa and residency permit. However, if the residency permit was not renewed, the employee becomes an illegal resident liable to arrest, detention and deportation, not the *kaf l*. Thus, the original idea of the *kaf l* taking responsibility for the *makf l* does not resonate in the new form. As Franz notes, the *kafala* as adapted to migrant labour, “violates both the letter and spirit of the legal institution,” where “something once associated with social protection has become more restrictive and punitive (Franz 2014, 101).

Kafala System in Action: A Case of Saudi Arabia

Between 1950 and 2005, the Gulf Cooperation Council’s (GCC) population grew tremendously; it increased from 4 million in the 6 countries that make the GCC to over 40

million, with 12.5 million of them being foreignersⁱ. Since the mid-1950s, the Arab States, and the Gulf countries in particular, have been the destination of many refugees. Consequently, their number increased from 1.3 million to 2 million in the 1980s (Alzahrani 2014). Moreover, population growth, economics, security and international relations are dynamics that affect each region's emigration and immigration policies. The GCC region has the highest labour migration because of the oil-based economy. As a result, the GCC states began initiating strict nationality and citizenship laws to ban immigrants from any political or socio-economic rights and to preserve the national identity (Appleyard 1999). Legislators in the GCC actively drafted a system to assure the interests of the local citizen over the migrant.ⁱⁱ Thus, the kafala system was born to govern the rights of the citizens and to control the entrance of migrants.

As Saudi Arabia perceives itself as an Islamic state, its laws are primary based on the Qur'an and the Sunnah. However, as any sovereign country, the government has introduced laws that aim to guard it against threats to its political territory. The kafala is one of these laws, although it has been criticised for its cruelty and its inconsistency to international human rights. It may come as a surprise that there is no single legal source that identifies the kafala system in Saudi Arabia. It could be described as a collection of policies premised on Saudi Labour law and Residency regulations. Further, the policies maintain a thorough distinction between domestic and non-domestic workers.

In an answer to frequent questions on the Islamic legal framework of recruiting foreign workers through *kafala* in Saudi Arabia, the Permanent Committee of Scientific Research and Fatwas published a long research paper to provide legal reasoning for the legality of *kafala* and the parameters that should be considered in its application (Jureidini and Hassan 2020). The committee started its presentation by confirming that recruiting foreign workers is part of the state policy to care for the interests of its people. Consequently, the administration of labour recruitment is subject to the approval of the King, as the head of the state and the one in charge of the affairs of Muslims, i.e. the *waliy al-amr* (Ibid). According to Islamic law, the *waliy al-amr* can issue laws to regulate people's lives, including businesses in a way that protects the rights of contractors and the needs of the society, provided that these laws do not contradict a Qur'anic injunction or a Prophetic instruction. Given his powers, the *waliy al-amr* may exercise *ijtihad* and enact laws that command people to follow a certain set of regulations. People should abide by these regulations, or otherwise, they will be "the transgressors" (Ibid).

Based on these arguments, the *kafala*/sponsorship laws are considered part of this *siyasa*. It is argued that the regulation of the process of *kafala* or hiring foreign workers is a task of the *waliy al-amr* or his representative. The regulation defines who should be recruited, conditions of their recruitment, rights and duties of both *kafals* (sponsors / employers) and the *makfals* (sponsored / employees). The main function of this regulation is to guarantee the interest of the work itself, the maintenance of security, the prevention of chaos and tension in the work environment. Once these regulations are set, both sides, employers and employees, should follow the contractual conditions and commit themselves to its conditions. In so doing, they follow the Qur'anic injunction, "O, you who believe, commit yourselves to your contracts"; and to the Prophetic directive, "Muslims must commit to their conditions, and whoever neglects them, he is from the transgressors." If they do not abide by them, then the *waliy al-amr* may discipline them in the way he thinks appropriate (Ibid).

The key legislation governing migrant workers other than domestic workers is the Labour Law approved by Royal Decree M/51, of 2005 and its Implementing Regulations. On

the other hand, any framework for regulating the employment of domestic workers came only in 2013 through Ministerial Decision No. 310 of 1434 H. The dichotomy regarding domestic and non-domestic workers continues in every piece of legislation. For instance, it is illegal to charge recruitment fees to workers in the case of non-domestic workers, while the same is not explicitly prohibited for domestic workers. Similarly, it is prohibited for employers to confiscate non-domestic migrant workers' passports. Such confiscation is subject to a 5,000 Saudi Arabian Riyal (SAR) (US\$ 1300) fine; while it is not explicitly prohibited in case of a domestic worker's passport. When it comes to working conditions, the difference becomes even starker. The rule is to allow for only 8 hours of work per day or 48 hours per week for non-domestic workers, while it is 15 hours per day for domestic workers. Further exceptions are provided with specified break conditions for non-domestic workers which is not the case with domestic workers. Even overtime payment conditions are not provided by the law for domestic workers. However, one exception to the general lopsided regulations can be seen in the case of shelters and protection services. Considering the highly exploitative nature of the employment and various incidences of abuse has led the Ministry of Labour and Social Development, in cooperation with the police, to operate a shelter in Riyadh to assist domestic workers in claiming their wages and returning home.

Saudi Arabia introduced labour reforms in March 2021 that will ease restrictions and allow some migrant workers to change jobs without employer consent under certain narrow circumstances, which is being hailed as a major reform of the Kafala system (Alsharif 2021). The reforms, however, do not go far enough to dismantle the abusive *kafala* (visa sponsorship) system. And they exclude migrant workers not covered by the labour law, including domestic workers and farmers, who are among the least protected and most vulnerable to abuse. They allow migrant workers to request an exit permit without the employer's permission for the first time but do not abolish the exit permit, which violates human rights. This makes the entire reform agenda too little too late, and definitely nothing for the domestic workers.

Identifying the Underlying Causes of Exploitation

Historian Omar Hesham Al Shehabi sees the Kafala System as an extension of British colonial policy in Bahrain. According to Al Shehabi, in the 1920s Britain attempted to establish greater control and regulation of migration within Bahrain. This was specially the case in regard to pearl diving industry, as tens of thousands of migrants would pour in from the surrounding areas during the harvest season. Because of Bahrain's small bureaucratic capacity, the British devised the strategy of having each ship captain, *nokhetha*, be responsible for the people on his boat, "where he had to report to the customs officials their number, names and their valid travel permits" (Al Shehabi 2019). Around that same time, No Objection Certificates (NOCs) were introduced for British personnel that wanted to bring their families to the Gulf. Once oil was found and migrant worker influxes skyrocketed, the *nokhetha* system and the NOCs were merged to facilitate administration. This period also saw the increase in application of NOCs to domestic workers, because local Bahrainis were seen as unfit for domestic work (Ibid). This system would spread throughout the region and would become legislated after the Gulf states attained independence.

Thus, the modern Kafala System is better described not as a continuity of Islamic *kafala* principles, but rather an extension of British colonial policy in the Middle East. This is helpful to understand because it reveals the initial motivations behind the Kafala System: to establish control over migrant worker bodies when faced with a weak state capacity. In the modern day, however, this type of "outsourcing" of immigration regulation to private citizens

cannot be explained by a lack of a bureaucracy robust enough to manage migration flows. A social reproductive approach will be useful to explore who benefits from their labour.

The conditions endured by women domestic migrant workers exist at the intersection of patriarchy-capitalism-colonialism, as performers of the gendered, devalued labour that domestic labour represents. Domestic work—the daily maintenance of households and the labour of caring for children and other dependents—is crucial work. It enables workers to go out into the world, reproduces a new generation of workers and citizens, and sustains relationships among parents, children and families. And yet, it is devalued, degraded and made invisible. Its degradation and invisibility are produced through processes of gendering that naturalize domestic and caring labours as women’s work, and racialization that naturalize low-wage, “dirty” jobs as the work of people of colour and immigrants (Nadasen and Williams 2009). Domestic work is a type of socially reproductive labour. In this context, social reproduction refers to “the activities and attitudes, behaviours and emotions, and responsibilities and relationships directly involved in maintaining life, on a daily basis and intergenerationally. It involves various kinds of socially necessary work—mental, physical, and emotional— aimed at providing the historically and socially, as well as biologically, defined means for maintaining and reproducing the population” (Laslett and Brenner 1989). Under Social Reproduction Theory (SRT), social reproduction is the mechanism by which workers’ labour power is replenished daily, and the working-class is reproduced intergenerationally. For example, families that rely on domestic workers to provide socially reproductive labour are essentially dependent on their employees to be able to work outside the household and receive wages to sustain themselves. This allows for middle class families to have a higher standard of living than they would otherwise have if a less exploitative environment where the cost of domestic labour was more prohibitive.

The kafil’s employer benefits as well. For highly demanding jobs that may prevent the workers from performing socially reproductive labour at home, the *kafil*’s employment is contingent on the domestic worker. By reproducing the *kafil*, domestic workers allow the *kafil*’s boss to exploit (extract surplus value) from the *kafil*. In fact, the Kafala System makes it so that the kafil’s boss receives racial and gendered subsidies from their employees’ domestic workers. Bosses of employees who can forgo domestic labour “consequently benefits doubly: from exploiting its worker and from the effective salary subsidy” that comes from a system of cheap (hyper exploitation), or, at times, not remunerated labour (appropriation) (Mcintyre and Nast 2011).

Hyper exploitation refers to domestic workers’ low-wage conditions. ILO estimates show that domestic workers usually make less than 50% of the average wage of the country where they work.ⁱⁱⁱ This is especially the case with domestic labour and other types of “unskilled” labour. The poor image of domestic labour can be explained through the ways in which it has been gendered and racialized. For example, domestic labour is devalued through centuries of labour gendering through dismissing these jobs as “labours of love” (Nadasen and Williams 2009). Moreover, domestic labour is heavily racialized (Harzig 2017). In the case of the Gulf, transregional migration systems have reinforced racial hierarchies associated with what was largely regarded as the “dirty work” of the household (Ibid). These systems have produced a labour that is undervalued and underpaid. Moreover, there are many restrictions on unionizing that prevent workers from bargaining for higher wages. The country with the most favourable policy towards collective bargaining in the Gulf is Bahrain; their Workers’ Trade Union Law of 2002 granted all migrant workers, except domestic workers, the right to belong to a union. Despite this codification of rights, however, most migrant

workers are unable to join a labour union for fear of losing their jobs and because of overwhelming language barriers given the diversity of home countries for migrant workers and the lack of resources given to union organization. Union regulations vary widely across the Gulf, though a more typical law is that of the Qatar labour code which allows a singular trade union, but excludes non-Qatari workers, effectively preventing unionizing.^{iv}

Facing international pressure, GCC countries have begun to implement marginal Kafala System reforms; although these policies look substantial on the surface, the vast majority fail to address the inherent power imbalance created by the system. Starting in 2005, countries like Jordan, Saudi Arabia, and Kuwait created labour protections that required a certain number of hours for continuous rest in a workday, a singular day off per week, and a maximum allowable work hours per week. Despite these advances for migrant workers, the laws do nothing to protect against abuse during the workday, there is little enforcement of these breaks, and Kuwait's maximum hours per week law excludes domestic labourers, one of the most vulnerable migrant worker populations (Murray 2020). The recent "landmark" reform in Qatar as of January 16th, 2020 was hailed as the "end of the Kafala system" given that it took away the requirements for migrants to obtain an exit permit to leave the country. The law requires a 72-hour notification to the employer with a four-year work ban and financial penalties if this is not done. The law, however, fails to recognize that the 72-hour period would be ineffective for migrant workers trying to flee an abusive employer: passports could be confiscated, more abuse could happen in response to the attempt to flee, and an employer could physically prevent a worker from leaving. In essence, the landmark law reform has little effect on the status quo, especially for the most vulnerable of domestic workers.

By employing a Social Reproduction Theory analysis, it is clear that the sponsors, employers of sponsors, and recruitment agencies all have a stake in exploiting and profiting off of these workers, made possible by the nexus of colonialism and patriarchy. Past attempts at reform will be of use as we look towards ways to fix or ameliorate this issue.

Conclusion

The Kafala sponsorship system has radically changed its form and spirit from the intended purpose in the traditional Islamic law. In its true form, as it is practiced today, it is no less than a modern day slavery. However, what makes it more peculiar is the way the Gulf states use it to systematically exploit a certain group of people who contribute disproportionately in national productivity. Further, while various reforms have ensued to modify or rationalise Kafala system, it has categorically excluded the domestic workers who are predominantly female. Through the Social Reproduction Theory, the invisibilisation of gendered domestic work can be understood. At the same time racial prejudice that makes the needs of the migrants second to the citizens and the conscious attempts at eliminating the possibility of citizenship for even second- generation migrants, suggest an invisibilisation of migrants. At the intersection of these three invisibilities, the invisibility of domestic sphere, the invisibility of female labour and the invisibility of migrants, put the female domestic migrant workers at the bottom of the ladder in an already exploitative system of Kafala sponsorship.

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